

Sonocatalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB) organic dye using MIL-88(Fe)/NaY/MnFe₂O₄ nanocomposite sonocatalyst: parametric & reusability studies

Meysam Sadeghi

Department of Chemistry, Lorestan University, Khoram-Ababd, Iran
Email: meysamsadeghi1364@gmail.com

Maryam Gholami

Department of Chemistry, Lorestan University, Khoram-Ababd, Iran
Email: Maryam.gholami78@yahoo.com

Pourya Zarshenas

Faculty of Chemistry & Petroleum Sciences, Shahid Beheshti University (SBU), Iran
Email: dr.pouryazarshenas@yahoo.com

Abstract

This research examined sonocatalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB) dye in the presence of MIL-88(Fe)/NaY/MnFe₂O₄ nanocomposite synthesized using the ultrasound assisted-hydrothermal route. Multiple identification techniques were utilized to investigate the MIL-88(Fe)/NaY/MnFe₂O₄ nanocomposite sonocatalyst involving FESEM, EDAX, FTIR, XRD and BET. The influences of various parameters like contact time, pH, initial MB concentration and sonocatalyst dosage were precisely studied. About 98.1% of MB dye degradation was achieved under the optimum parameter conditions i.e. at pH of 7, 25 mg/L of initial MB concentration and 0.5 g/L of MIL-88(Fe)/NaY/MnFe₂O₄ dosage within 60 min. The enhancement of sonocatalytic activities can be related to the function of NaY zeolite as trap state for the electron. The scavenger tests outcomes demonstrated that the sono-generated hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$) would play an important role in the MB degradation. Additionally, the MIL-88(Fe)/NaY/MnFe₂O₄ was quite stable since the efficiency of MB degradation gained in the four run was 93.7%.

Keywords: sonocatalytic, degradation, methylene blue, MIL-88(Fe)/NaY/MnFe₂O₄, nanocomposite.